

NEW NANOCOMPOSITE ELASTOMERIC SANDWICH FOR HIGH STRAIN AND HIGH STIFFNESS ADAPTIVE A/C STRUCTURES

23rd International Conference on Composite Materials, Belfast, August 2023

NRC · CMRC · AIRBUS

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Where do we have the need for adaptive / morphing materials for future Airbus products?

Ecological low drag and low noise aircraft - Step/gap-less, laminar flow

Lightweight, improved flight control & passenger comfort - Adaptive Wings (UpNext eXtra performance wing demonstrator)

High stretchable but stiff material and a trade between:

- Actuation force
- Skin waviness
- Flutter

Examples and research for lateral seamless connections:

SARISTU project 2018

- Adaptive winglet
- Casted silicone block
- **Heavy, attachment concept, actuation force**

<https://www.aemac.org/>

FlexSys / AFRL - 2018

- Lateral transition between fixed and moving A/C part
- Folding mechanism
- **Aerodynamically suboptimal**

<https://www.flexsys.com/flexfoil>

NASA - FLEXSEL - 2020

- Low noise side edge fitting
- Polyurethane EP1150 from Eager Plastic as skin material + elastomeric foam core for installation
- **Low stiffness under cruise, only for hidden A/C areas**

Sreekantamurthy et al, AIAA Scitech 2014-0509

FlexMat - 2020

- Lateral transition between fixed and moving A/C part
- EPDM block with CF Epoxy-Fibers
- **Actuator force, integration**

Credit: [**Conflicting requirements of deformability & rigidity** to carry \(aerodynamic\) loads, and aerospace requirements appropriate solutions \(environmental conditions, flight cycles, fluids, loads\)](https://www.dlr.de/fo/fo.nsf/(openDocument?symbol=00000000000000000000000000000000&open=1)DLR (CC BY-NC-ND 3.0)</p></div><div data-bbox=)

Our proposed solution: a Nanocomposite Elastomeric Sandwich

- **Cooperation agreement between NRC-CNRC and Airbus** in place, both parties with in-kind contribution to develop high stretchable in-plane, higher stiffness out-of-plane material.
- Solution: **Tailorable nanocomposite sandwich** → **low membrane stiffness** combined with high stretchability but **high out-of-plane stiffness**.

Nanocomposite Elastomeric Sandwich: Engineering seamless stretchable seals

- Retains **good stretchability** with **increased resistance to out-of-plane loading**
- **Customizable sandwich material** according to the specific needs

Carbon Nanotube - Thermoplastic Polyurethane

- Requirement sets based on **more-electrical A320-style aircraft (1b)** and **UAM vehicle (2)**
- **50% strain performed under environmental conditions** – covers a wide range of application scenarios

Table 1. Overview of the four sets of requirements

Specific Requirement	Unit	Requirements Set 1a	Requirements Set 1b	Requirements Set 1c	Requirements Set 2
Strain under environmental conditions	%	50	50	50	50
highest Temp.	°C	+85	+85	+85	+85
lowest Temp.	°C	-55	-55	-55	-30
resistance against SKYDROL	-	yes	no	no	no
resistance against kerosine	-	yes	yes	no	no
resistance against water	-	yes	yes	yes	yes
resistance against UV	-	yes	yes	yes	yes
resistance against erosion (water droplet, ice, ...)	-	yes	yes	yes	yes

Maximum Principal Strain

Concern: strain concentrations near the edges. Localised 93% for global 50%

- TPU, silicone and EPDM neat materials
- Temperature dependence of the storage modulus (Fig. 1) – Stiffening behaviour at low temperatures
- Quasi-static tensile tests to 50% strain performed under environmental conditions (Fig. 2) – modulus increase 1st vs. 10th cycle

Fig. 1. DMA curves for elastomers.

Fig. 2. Stress-strain curves for TPU and EPDM.
- 1st and 10th cycle represented

- Solvent/non-solvent method**

Nanocry NC7000 MWCNTs + thermoplastic polyurethane (TPU)

- Controlled polymer adsorption onto CNTs → High-nanotube-content (~ 15-80%) nonwoven sheets, tailorable properties
- Convenient handling (use as a sheet vs. powder or dispersed CNTs)
- Cost-effective, industrial-grade CNT powders

Martinez-Rubi *et al*, ACS AMI 2017 | Jakubinek *et al*, MRS Adv 2019

- **ADAPTED solvent/non-solvent procedure** for uncured EPDM
Targeting 10–30% CNTs for high stretching goal

CNTs: MWCNTs (NC7000, Nanocyl)
SWCNTs (Tuball, OCSiAl)

EPDM: EPDM/O5 (Kraiburg)

- **Method effective** for \sim 15 to >50 wt% CNTs
- **Recover \sim 70% of the EPDM** in the coagulation and filtration process

- After recovery from solution: CNT-EPDM/05 sheets do not crosslink (not elastomeric); no DSC-peak, can be re-molded
- Still, observe **significantly higher tensile stress** at equivalent strain vs. neat EPDM (0.4 MPa at 25% strain)
- Optimum in properties at ~ 30 wt% CNTs

1. “Cold” compression-mold (110 °C)

2. Insert nanocomposite layers, co-cure by hot-pressing (170 °C)

15 cm square → 2 “sandwiches”
+ baseline coupons

3. Test Coupons

Cross-section

- CNT-EPDM/05 | EPDM/05 | CNT-EPDM/05
- Nanocomposite crosslinks when co-cured with neat EPDM/05 core producing elastic material
- All sandwich samples deflect similarly in simple cantilever bending
- **Increased stiffness but higher residual strain (vs. neat EPDM)**
- **High cyclic strain (50% and 100%) achieved**

Elastic behaviour of nanocomposite sandwich

Cyclic tensile, 100% strain; Showing 1st, 9th and 10th cycles

- Variation of layer composition & thickness
 - CNT type (NC7000 MWCNTs, Tuball SWCNTs)
 - CNT wt% (from 0 to 23)
 - Layer thickness (nanocomposite and neat EPDM core)
- Testing in tension (ISO 37/ASTM D412) and flexure (ASTM D790)

Nanocomposite layers			Neat polymer	Multilayer (sandwich) performance		
CNT type	CNT wt%	Layer thickness (mm)	Thickness (mm)	Stress @ 50% strain (10 th cycle, MPa)	Residual strain (10 th cycle, %)	Bending modulus (MPa)
N/A	0		1.5	0.5	4	4.5
MWCNT	12.8	0.42	0.72	1.9	15	24
MWCNT	15.4	0.22	0.91	1.8	14	20
MWCNT	17	0.21	1.23	1.5	15	26
MWCNT	17	0.24	2.64	1.0	13	11
MWCNT	23	0.15	1.29	2.6	19	30
SWCNT	15	0.24	1.23	2.7	16	27
SWCNT	15	0.26	1.48	3.0	23	26
SWCNT	15	0.30	1.50	3.4	24	25
SWCNT	15	0.44	1.17	4.8	26	32

Bending modulus and tensile stress

Note. Residual strain represented by proportionally datapoint size.

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Bending and membrane stiffness (scaled to 2mm thickness)

Membrane stiffness: $thickness * E_{mem}$
 Bending stiffness: $thickness^3 * E_{bend}$

Note. Residual strain represented by proportionally datapoint size.

Challenge 1: Residual Strain

- 50% stretching target informed by preliminary designs
- **Pre-load specimen** (initial length L_0); Cycle between L_1 and L_2 ($L_2=1.5*L_1$) at room temperature
- **Stable cycling achieved (50% extension) with nanocomposite sandwich**

Challenge 2: Low-temperature operation conditions

- **Electrical conductivity of CNT as enabler for Joule heating**
- Potential solution to address high residual strain and higher actuation load at $-55\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$
- Cyclic performance comparable to typical room-temperature testing

Benchtop heating tests (ambient conditions)

Test chamber @ $-55\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ (IR camera limited to $>-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$)

Aim: Strength test – Does the seal work under 50 % cyclic strain ?

- Non-standard testing – own test rig
- Test velocity: 5 mm/min; Temperature: RT
- Load introduction clamping

Step-gapless adaptive trailing edge demonstrator

Conclusion:

- **Successful CNT integration with the EPDM** via CNT-TPU process adaptation;
- **Production of CNT-EPDM nanocomposite elastomeric sandwich;**
- **CNT integration increased out-of-plane stiffness** but also the tensile stiffness and residual strain
- **Higher modulus and stiffness out-of-plane vs. in-plane**
- **50% cyclic deformation was achieved** (pre-stretched to maintain the skin in tension for the full cycle)
- **Joule heating** as enabler for low-temperature operation conditions (-55°C)

Outlook:

- **Neat elastomer modification** to improve the low temperature behaviour;
- **Optimization of nanocomposite sandwich layer** thicknesses and composition (CNT content) to demonstration targets for strain and bending stiffness
- **Integration thermoset CFRP** into nanocomposite elastomeric sandwich for load introduction areas;
- **Generic functional demonstrator** to validate the step-gapless connection of a moving aileron and a fixed wing structure.

Fundings

- Airbus Central Research & Technology
- NRC Low Emission Aviation Program

Supplier

- Kraiburg

Airbus

- Paul Mühlthaler (X-Labs), Colin West

National Research Council of Canada

- Behnam Ashrafi, Hugo Laurin, Meysam Rahmat, Steven Roy, Sam Xian

Thank you for your attention

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